

>>Did the Dæther¹ respond?

In this letter:

→ Small update from Tuesday's publishing on MIMS 2.1.212

MIMS 2.1.212a - Fibonacci Pressure

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Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/31rtAlr>

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¹ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

Re: Is there a “fibonacci² pressure”?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

Just in two days, once again the theory receives support. Nothing big to post here. Just some arrows:

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/6/22, 9:46 AM

Figure 1 - Bitcoin Futures, pressure? Or conspiracy?; credit: Thinkorswim/author
What you may not see is the BTF fell below the Bollinger Band, and channel, and the Fibonacci “fan” appeared to push the data into the other channel.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

² Remember, the 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13 sequence is a key to the EPEMC, MIMS, and Big G diagram framework, and this is an important example of self-consistency.
https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
https://www.academia.edu/65563310/MIMS_1_01_03_Philosophy_Integration_Self_test